

Impact of Collaborative Robots on Human Trust, Anxiety, and Workload: Experiment Findings

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Abstract. This work proposes an experiment setup and its protocols to investigate the impact of cobot’s size, speed and collaboration modes on different human factors including trust, propensity to trust, anxiety, and mental workload. The setup and the protocols supported the execution of different experiments where the 29 participants were asked to complete the Tower of Hanoi in collaboration with a cobot. The setup and the protocols provide a ready-to-use solution to expand experiments for further studies. Moreover, statistical analysis of the results shows higher cobot speeds increased trust propensity despite not significantly affecting overall trust or anxiety. Collaboration modes significantly influenced perceived workload and task performance, with the “Collaboration with Trigger” mode resulting in lower mental workload but longer task completion times. No significant differences were found in human factors concerning cobot size, indicating that variations in size do not significantly impact trust, propensity to trust, anxiety, or workload. Additionally, the collaboration mode with cobots notably affects workload perception and task performance, with specific modes reducing perceived effort but not necessarily improving task efficiency.

Keywords: Cobots · Human Robot Collaboration · Collaborative robots · Human factors · Ergonomics

1 Introduction

Industrial robots were initially developed to substitute human labour in tasks deemed hazardous or monotonous [13]. However, over the past decade, there has been a notable pivot towards fostering coexistence and collaboration between humans and robots with the advent of collaborative robots, also known as cobots. This shift aims to enhance operational efficiency and flexibility, concurrently augmenting employees’ working conditions and well-being [34].

However, despite offering soft interaction modes supporting collaboration [21], a cobot remains fundamentally an automation device. Consequently, as with any automation device, the effective and safe integration of cobots into industrial environments requires an understanding of how workers react and operate with it and what Human Factors (HFs) play a role in the interaction.

HFs are studied within a scientific discipline that focuses on the interactions between humans and system elements, aiming to mitigate human error, which can lead to adverse outcomes if not addressed [14]. This field, known as HFs engineering, involves designing equipment and systems that align with operators' mental and physical characteristics, thereby optimising system performance and human well-being.

This work and its associated experiment concentrate on examining *mental workload* [26], *trust* [20], including a specific focus on the *propensity to trust* [15] and *anxiety* [10] within collaborative robotics and Human Robot Interaction (HRI), employing the Tower of Hanoi (TOH) as the experimental framework. The selection of these particular aspects follows from extensive studies in the fields of HFs in collaborative robotics and HRI, which encompass a broad range of dimensions such as, in addition to the four already mentioned, physical ergonomics, acceptance, usability, and many others [12, 33]. The experiment results provide statistical evidence on the dynamics of the selected HFs in relation to the size, speed, and collaborative modes of cobots.

This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 investigates the role of HF in HRI evaluating previous works that propose TOH. Section 3 presents the setup of the experiments with all the different collaboration modes, while Section 4 outlines the results of the experiments, with valuable insights regarding HRI. Conclusions and future research directions are presented in Section 5.

2 Human Factors, Serious Games and Cobots

2.1 Human Factors

Collaborative robotics brought attention and interest to the centrality of people's feelings and well-being in industrial environments. This leads to more recent in-depth studies on HFs. This research builds on these studies by examining various interaction modes involving different cobots and variables. It also establishes a flexible experimental framework, facilitating future investigations into additional aspects and factors.

Mental workload. It refers to the cognitive demands imposed on an individual during task performance [26]. *Mental workload* encompasses various cognitive processes such as attention, memory, decision-making, and problem-solving. A collaborative robot acting as a leader and follower has been used to study the impacts on stress and trust [31]. A few frameworks have been developed to assess the *mental workload* in working with a cobot [36, 44]. Furthermore, research on HRI indicates that designing intuitive interfaces and providing adequate support can mitigate *mental workload* and enhance user performance [46].

Trust. It refers to an individual’s belief or confidence in another entity or system’s reliability, integrity, and competence [?]. *Trust* is crucial in HRI, influencing user acceptance, cooperation, and reliance on robotic systems. Properly calibrated *trust* in robotic systems is critical and can be enabled through robot explanations of their behaviour [11]. As robots perform increasingly complex tasks in environments shared with human teammates, the need for explainable robot behaviour will gain relevance. Previous work in HFs has explicitly explored the importance of user *trust* in automated systems [25]. The focus is not always on increasing user *trust*, but on properly calibrating *trust* to use robotic systems. For this purpose, many different questionnaires and tests exist to estimate the *trust* felt by a human being, including Interpersonal Trust Questionnaire [42]; International Personality Item Pool [9]; Negative Attitudes Towards Robots Scale [37]; Trust Perception Scale for Human-Robot Interaction (TPS-HRI) [43].

Propensity to trust. It refers to an individual’s inherent inclination or predisposition to trust other entities or systems [15]. The *propensity of trust* varies among individuals and is influenced by factors such as personality traits, past experiences, cultural background, and situational contexts. Few studies have examined how the *propensity to trust* influences user reliance on automation. Recent works have adopted the Propensity to Trust Machines Scale (PTM) to measure *propensity to trust* [22, 30], which typically consists of a series of statements or items that respondents rate based on their level of agreement or disagreement.

Anxiety. It refers to a state of uneasiness, apprehension, or worry experienced by individuals when faced with perceived threats or uncertainties [10]. *Anxiety* may arise due to factors such as unfamiliarity with robots, concerns about privacy or safety, or uncertainty about the robot’s intentions or capabilities and it is probably one of the human emotions that is most present during interactions of every nature [32]. Studies on anxiety towards robots produced various results [35], showing how this factor is related to cultural differences [2], age [23] and anxiety attitudes [38]. In the industrial context, *anxiety* is mainly measured through the State-Trait Anxiety Index (STAI), a subjective test that discerns between “state anxiety”, i.e., the anxiety that someone feels at the moment he/she is filling in the questionnaire, and “trait anxiety”, which is, instead, the feeling of anxiety that is congenital and typical of somebody’s character [24]. Furthermore, an anxiety scale was developed for robotic systems [39] and used to measure anxiety that prevents people from interacting with robots.

2.2 The Tower of Hanoi

To investigate HFs in HRI, it is beneficial to utilise a controlled setting where consistent rules, behaviours, and protocols can be applied, similar to those used in a serious game. Serious games are games designed for purposes beyond mere entertainment [27], including education, training, research, and in this case, the exploration of HRI dynamics. In the context of HRI, serious games usually involve the so-called *social robots*. Examples of these social robots are *iCat* [1] and *Leonardo* [8], applied using the Wizard of Oz method. This method involves a human operator (the “wizard”), who controls the robot responses, often behind

the scenes. At the same time, experiment participants interact with the robot as if it is fully automated [7]. This method is widely used since it provides a flexible way to implement complex robot behaviour within a quick time-scale [48].

Recent advancements in robotics, such as the extreme ease of programming, make less relevant this control scheme, empowering the use of autonomous robot systems directly to engage in interactive in-game scenarios with humans [28]. Consequently, this research opts out of the Wizard of Oz methodology, favouring a fully automated approach. This enables the realistic simulation of an industrial context that performs predefined automation tasks without the flexibility typically introduced by human intervention, as in the Wizard of Oz method. This environment is set up through a simple yet meaningful game where an autonomous robot and a human collaborate to execute a joint task: the TOH.

The TOH, traditionally recognised as a mathematical puzzle, acquires a broader function as a serious game when applied in studying HRI. The TOH uses three vertical pegs and a number d of disks with a central hole and increasing external diameter. Typically, the game begins with all disks stacked on one peg to form a complete tower, although there are no strict rules requiring this starting arrangement as long as it adheres to the game’s rules. The final goal of the game is to build a full stack in one of the pegs making one move at a time, following three rules: i) Only one disk can be moved at a time; ii) Each move consists of taking the top disk from one of the pegs and placing it in another peg; iii) No disk may be placed on top of a smaller disk.

The TOH can be considered complex from a problem-solving perspective because it requires strategic planning and foresight. Even if the game has a recursive solution, the time framework and the pressure to solve the puzzle in a minimum number of moves make it mentally demanding [18].

Many studies using the TOH have been performed in the HRI field. Several works adopted this game as a task to be performed by a robot in collaboration with a child to assess i) children’s learning process with different levels of robot vocalisation [49], ii) robot intervention effectiveness regarding a voluntary turn-taking interaction [5] and iii) completion rate changes with the introduction of a pre-task instruction session with the robot as the teacher [41]. A separate study, not focusing on children, illustrated that the physical involvement of a robot in task execution enhances both performance and social perception by humans [47]. Conversely, research into the impacts of anthropomorphism in robotics unexpectedly showed that the propensity to offer assistance to a robot facing malfunctions diminishes when the robot exhibits more human-like characteristics, following a collaboration task on the TOH [40]. In other research, the TOH has been used to measure stress and fatigue levels of operators while doing a task in collaboration with a robotic arm, assessing the cognitive fatigue and workload [3, 16]. Likewise, this work expects to extend the use of TOH to study HFs in collaborative robotics.

3 System and Experiment Setup

This work sheds light on the HRI focusing on collaborative robots. It proposes a robotic system that enables a set of experiments to investigate HRI through the TOH. The system is complemented by the formulation of various experiments alongside their execution protocols, which encompass questionnaires and analysis methods. This supported the experimental activities detailed in this study and opened pathways for further extension and diverse analyses in the future.

The system's setup includes two different types of cobots, an igus ReBeL and an ABB GoFa 15000, 3D-printed TOH's disks and pegs, a vision system, a Graphical User Interface (GUI) and ArUco markers, as depicted in Fig. 1. Using two different cobots enables the study of the influence of robot characteristics, such as size and speed, on HFs.

Fig. 1: ABB GoFa and Igus ReBeL setups; participants engaging with the cobot

3.1 Experiment Protocol

The experiment protocol is divided into three phases: i) pre-task phase, ii) task phase and iii) post-task phase.

Volunteers learn the TOH rules, research goals, and the cobot type in the pre-task phase. After consenting, they wear devices to record baseline physiological data for 3-4 minutes. A simplified TOH helps to acquaint themselves with the rules and the task. This phase ends with a questionnaire on prior robot interactions, initial trust, and anxiety levels.

During the task phase, participants enter the workspace with the robot to commence the task. They select collaboration modes (triggered, alternated with trigger, alternated with countdown or mixed, later detailed) from the GUI before initiating the game. The participants make the first move in any collaboration mode, while physiological data collection, game events and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are collected.

The study considers three variables: cobot model (i.e., igus ReBeL, ABB GoFa 15000) and hence its size (respectively small and big), cobot speed (fast (1500 mm/s) or slow (300 mm/s)), and collaboration mode.

Table 1: Experiments

ID	Participants	Size	Speed	Collaboration Mode
E1	4	Igus (small)	Slow (300 mm/s)	Triggered Collaboration
E2	6	Igus (small)	Slow (300 mm/s)	Alternated with Countdown
E3	3	Gofa (big)	Slow (300 mm/s)	Alternated with Countdown
E4	5	Gofa (big)	Fast (1500 mm/s)	Alternated with Countdown
E5	6	Gofa (big)	Fast (1500 mm/s)	Alternated with Trigger
E6	5	Gofa (big)	Fast (1500 mm/s)	Mixed Collaboration

Triggered Collaboration defines a collaboration mode where the robot intervenes only when the participant wants, using the GUI. *Alternated Collaboration with Trigger* is a turn-taking-based collaboration where the robot intervenes only after the participants' commands (the participants have the time they want to think and complete their move). *Alternated Collaboration with Countdown* is a turn-taking-based collaboration where the robot moves every 5 seconds from when it has completed its previous move. *Mixed Collaboration* involves turn-taking between human and robot after 7 consecutive moves. Experiments are categorised based on the combination of these variables, enabling statistical analysis to identify differences caused by varying experimental conditions.

Once the task phase has been completed, the participant moves toward the third and last phase of the experiment where the participant fills in the post-task questionnaires. The overall duration of the three steps is around 25-30 minutes.

Table 1 resumes all experiments with their main characteristics. The current study makes statistical analysis (Section 3.2) by comparing one variable at a time and detecting possible differences caused by the different experiment conditions.

3.2 Analysis Protocol

During the pre-task phase, participants complete several questionnaires: an initial demographic survey and three tests assessing HF: the PTM [30], STAI [45], and the TPS-HRI [43]. The same questionnaires are administered in the post-task phase, except for the demographic survey. They are supplemented with the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [17] and questions about the experiment and HRI quality. Table 2 provides an overview of questionnaires included in the protocol proposed by this work.

In addition, a set of KPIs reported has been defined to assess the quality and efficiency of the task execution (Table 3).

The analysis of data is performed by making use of various statistical tests: i) Student's t-test, ii) One-way ANOVA, iii) Mixed ANOVA. T-test is used to compare the means of two normally distributed samples; ANOVA and Mixed ANOVA detect differences between groups divided into two independent variables: the between-subject variable and the within-subject variable (*i.e.*, the

³ Coefficient Of Performance: the ratio between optimal and total moves.

Table 2: Questionnaires

Questionnaire	Description (Phases)
Demographic questionnaire	A series of questions for the identification of the participant characteristics (e.g., age, sex) (Pre-task)
PTM	A series of statements regarding their <i>propensity to trust</i> the collaborative robot that respondents rate based on their level of agreement or disagreement. (Pre-task, post-task)
STAI (short)	A subjective test that discerns between “state anxiety” and “trait anxiety”. The version used in this research, however, is a shortened one, that pivots only on “state anxiety”, leaving the other trait apart. (Pre-task, post-task)
TPS-HRI (short)	A series of Likert-scale-based statements to measure the extent to which individuals <i>trust</i> a robot in various aspects of interaction, such as reliability, competence, predictability, and intentionality (Pre-task, post-task)
NASA-TLX (short)	An assessment on six dimensions that capture different aspects of perceived <i>mental workload</i> . (Post-task)
HRI quality questionnaire	Questions to investigate how the human has perceived the collaboration between the operator and the cobot. (Post-task)

Table 3: Key Performance Indicators

KPI	Description
Effectiveness	Whether the game has been solved or not
Time-to-task	Time to complete the game
Human Errors	Number of non-legit configurations made by volunteer
Robot Errors	Number of disks misplaced by the robot
COP ³	Efficiency of the solution in terms of the number of moves
Cobot moves	Number of times the cobot makes a move

repeated measures). These statistical tests were chosen because they are well-suited for analysing differences between groups (t-tests and ANOVA) and examining interactions between multiple factors (mixed ANOVA), which is essential for understanding collaborative robotics’s complex and multifaceted impacts on human factors. Alternative tests might not provide the same level of detail or may be less appropriate for the experimental design used in this study.

The following statistical terms have been used for the results presented in Section 4: F (*F-statistic*), p (*p-value*), η_p^2 (*Partial Eta Squared*) and *Time*.

F : the F-statistic is a ratio used in the context of ANOVA to compare the variance among group means to the variance within the groups. A higher F-value indicates a more significant disparity between group means, suggesting that at least one group mean is significantly different. The F-statistic helps to determine if these differences are statistically significant. It is calculated based on the degrees of freedom between groups (numerator) and the variance within groups (denominator).

p : it represents the probability of obtaining the observed results, or more extreme, assuming that the null hypothesis is true. It is a key indicator of statistical significance. A low p-value (typically less than 0.05) suggests that the observed data are unlikely under the null hypothesis, leading to its rejection in favour of the alternative hypothesis. Conversely, a high p-value indicates that the observed data are consistent with the null hypothesis, suggesting no statistically significant effect.

η_p^2 : it is a measure of effect size used in the context of ANOVA to quantify the proportion of the total variance in the dependent variable that is attributable to an independent variable, after accounting for other variables or factors in the model. It ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating a larger effect size or greater explanatory power of the independent variable on the dependent variable. According to conventional benchmarks, a value of 0.01 is considered a small effect, 0.06 a medium effect, and 0.14 a significant effect.

Time: the within-variable is called *Time*, and its values are “Before” or “After” (*i.e.*, pre-task and post-task).

3.3 System Architecture

The architecture developed connects all the system components, as depicted in Fig. 2a. An orchestrator is in charge of the coordination of the task execution and the communication between the vision system, the cobot and the GUI, depicted in Fig. 2b.

The participants can interact directly with the TOH or with the GUI, sending activation signals to the cobot, which the orchestrator elaborates. The orchestrator receives the current TOH state thanks to the vision system, computes the optimal next move, and, if required, sends the instructions to the cobot. All the software components communicate by exchanging JSON messages over MQTT.

The communication method between the orchestrator and the robot depends on the collaborative robot model used in the experiment. The ABB GoFa 15000 establishes a direct connection with the orchestrator using Socket communication. Conversely, with the igus ReBeL, the orchestrator employs the MQTT protocol to communicate with an industrial Raspberry Pi board, triggering the cobot’s physical digital inputs.

The system is also capable of collecting physiological data (e.g., using Polar Verity Sense armband, Polar H10 chest band) from participants to analyse heart rate variability and physiological data, relying on an IIoT platform to create human-digital twins [6].

4 Results and Discussion

The experiments involved a total of $V = 29$ volunteers ($M = 20$, $F = 9$). The demographic composition suggests a youthful participant pool, with almost 70% of people younger than 30. 62% of the participants reported that they had never worked with collaborative robots. Among those who had previous interactions

Fig. 2: Architecture and GUI

with cobots, the experiences were largely positive, except for one participant who recounted an adverse incident in a laboratory setting.

4.1 Speed Impact on Human Factors

Contrary to expectations, the tests revealed that higher cobot speed positively influences the *propensity to trust*, measuring increased levels post-task. Mixed-design ANOVA revealed a significant main effect ($F(1, 6) = 21.440$, $p = .004$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.781$), which underlines that the *propensity to trust* changed from the pre-task phase to the post-task one. However, speed does not significantly impact *trust* or *anxiety*. These findings suggest that while cobot speed influences the *propensity to trust*, other factors such as predictability, safety and reliability may play a more substantial role in determining *trust*. Additionally, it is important to note that numerous participants expressed concerns about the cobot's pace in the post-task assessments of experiments with a slow-speed setting. Many stated, “The cobot is too slow. I prefer to work alone since I am faster, even if I am not sure I am making the correct move.”

Further exploration of this finding might also consider findings from additional studies, suggesting that *trust* is influenced not merely by the speed but broadly by the robots' movement patterns and their predictability [4, 29]. In the TOH, the predictability of each cobot's movement is notably high, as the participant can observe the cobot's movements before the commencement of the activity and is familiar with its designated operational zone.

4.2 Collaboration Mode Impact on Human Factors

The results show that *trust* ($F(1, 13) = 1307.80$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.629$) and *propensity to trust* ($F(1, 13) = 272.305$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.954$) increased after collaboration in all modes, with no significant differences between them ((Fig. 3a, Fig. 3b). The *mental workload* was lowest in the *Alternated Collaboration with Trigger* ($F(2, 13) = 4.899$, $p < .05$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.430$).

The ANOVA revealed a significant effect of the collaboration mode on the perceived workload ($F(2, 13) = 4.899, p < .05, \eta_p^2 = 0.430$). Fig. 3c qualitatively shows the difference between the means of the three samples, underlying how the *Collaboration with Trigger* has a lower NASA-TLX score. Results suggest a significant effect of collaboration mode on the subjective assessment regarding the perceived workload, with post hoc analyses revealing a lower level of mental workload in volunteers that worked in *Collaboration with Trigger*.

Fig. 3: Results

In terms of performance, the *Alternated Collaboration with Trigger* resulted in significantly longer task completion times ($F(2, 13) = 4.624, p < .05, \eta_p^2 = 0.416$). Responses to the HRI questionnaire revealed differences in perceptions of task-solving abilities and willingness to use the system in everyday life across collaboration modes: participants in *Alternated Collaboration with Trigger* showed a more neutral opinion on the idea that working alone is better than working with the robot ($p < .05$), while the other volunteers disagreed with it; regarding usability, cobot in *Mixed Collaboration* resulted in the one that people would use more in their everyday life ($p < .05$). There was also a discrepancy between perceived understanding of the task algorithm and actual task performance: when asked to indicate the optimal successive move in a random TOH configuration with 6 disks, only 60% guessed the right choice, suggesting a potential false belief about comprehension induced by robot collaboration.

Alternated Collaboration with Trigger resulted in fewer cobot moves but more total moves to complete tasks than in other *Alternated Collaboration* modes ($U = 24, p < .05$). In *Alternated Collaboration with Trigger*, participants preferred to solve the game alone as a personal challenge and were less motivated to activate the robot. This conclusion agrees with other research exploring the differences between similar collaboration modes (voluntary interaction and turn-taking)[5]. Nevertheless, there exists a discrepancy when looking at performance results: people who worked voluntary interaction also performed better, in terms of the number of moves, with respect to the turn-taking, while in our research, the analysis on COP showed the opposite outcomes, detecting better levels of performance in volunteers in alternated collaboration.

4.3 Size Impact on Human Factors

Analysis of different cobot sizes shows no significant differences in propensity to trust, trust, anxiety, or mental workload. Despite variations in cobot size, human perceptions remain consistent. Hence, it is possible to conclude that cobot size does not significantly affect human factors.

At first glance, these results seem to be at odds compared to existing works [19], which identified the robot’s size as a factor that considerably impacts human anxiety. Nonetheless, on a deeper inspection, *anxiety* has been identified only with robot models with more than 1.8m reach, while both Gofa and ReBeL are much smaller. Furthermore, according to this work, the most significant change in *anxiety* happened while the volunteers were sitting; the standing position returned lower changes in *anxiety* instead. The volunteers used a standing position in every experiment of the current study, which could be another explanation for these different results.

4.4 Summary of Results

Table 4 summarises the experimental results, providing a comprehensive overview of the key findings and observations from the study.

Table 4: Summary of Results

Variable	IDs	Main Results
<i>Triggered Collaboration</i>	E1	No effects on HFs; in Triggered Collaboration mode, humans tend not to activate the cobot
<i>Size</i>	E2, E3	Size does not affect any HF
<i>Velocity</i>	E3, E4	Velocity affects partially propensity to trust
<i>Alternated and Mixed Collaboration</i>	E4, E5, E6	<i>Alternated with Trigger</i> has the lowest mental workload, the highest time to complete the task and the most neutral opinion on the importance of the collaboration with the robot; <i>trust</i> and <i>propensity to trust</i> greatly increases after the task in all modes; mixed collaboration has the highest perceived usability

Despite the thoroughness of the experiments, limitations include a relatively small sample size and young participants. However, the setup and the protocols developed in this research hold relevance for future works as they provide a ready-to-use solution to expand experiments for further studies. Future research will involve a broader range of participants and incorporate tasks more realistic for an industrial environment.

5 Conclusions

This work investigates the impact of cobot size, speed, and collaboration modes on HFs like *trust*, *propensity to trust*, *anxiety*, and *mental workload*. *Trust* and *propensity to trust* cobots increased across all three *Alternated Collaboration* modes, while *mental workload* was lower in *Collaboration with Trigger*, albeit at the expense of time. *Anxiety* remained mostly unaffected. Experiments showed that the collaboration robots led to an increased perceived understanding of TOH solution algorithm, but further trials on increased difficulty tasks suggest that this sensation could be a false belief.

From the practical perspective, the study highlights that collaboration modes significantly affect perceived workload and task performance. Specifically, the *Collaboration with Trigger* mode, which resulted in lower mental workload but longer task completion times, suggests that different modes of interaction need to be carefully chosen based on the specific task requirements and worker preferences. This insight can help managers design work processes that balance efficiency with employee well-being.

Furthermore, understanding that cobot *size* does not significantly impact *trust*, *propensity to trust*, *anxiety*, or *workload* can simplify decision-making regarding deploying different models. Managers can focus on other factors, such as speed and collaboration mode, to improve human-robot collaboration without worrying about the physical size of the cobots affecting human factors adversely.

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